

Drug abuse and laws in Pakistan

*Hafsa Afzaal

** Dr. Tansif Ur Rehman

*** Shoaib Tanoli

**** Mehran Ali Tunio

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* Hafsa Afzaal is a student of law at Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

** Dr. Tansif Ur Rehman is a visiting faculty at the Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

*** Shoaib Tanoli is a student of law at Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

**** Mehran Ali Tunio is a student of law at Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

Note: The authors have no conflict of interest to declare

Authors Biography

*Hafsa Afzaal is a student of BA-LLB at the Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education

**Dr. Tansif Ur Rehman is a visiting faculty at the Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan. He has been a reviewer for various reputed national and international journals for the last three years. He has 93 publications (articles and chapters), seven books, over 23 years of teaching, and 16 years of research experience.

***Shoaib Tanoli is a student of BA-LLB at the Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

**** Mehran Ali Tunio is a student of BA-LLB at the Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

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Regards,

Hafsa Afzaal

Dadabhoy Institute of Higher

Education

Abstract

Drug abuse is a pervasive global issue with severe consequences for individuals and society at large. This abstract explores the multifaceted nature of drug abuse, encompassing both legal and illicit substances. The prevalence of substance misuse contributes to numerous health, social, and economic challenges. Individuals engaging in drug abuse often face deteriorating physical and mental health, strained relationships, and diminished productivity. Moreover, drug-related crimes and the burden on healthcare systems amplify the societal impact. Prevention and intervention strategies are critical to addressing this complex problem, involving education, treatment, and policy initiatives. Understanding the underlying factors contributing to drug abuse, such as socioeconomic disparities and mental health issues, is essential for implementing effective and targeted interventions. A holistic and collaborative approach is necessary to mitigate the pervasive effects of drug abuse on individuals and communities.

Keywords: addiction, illicit drugs, mental health, narcotics, rehabilitation, substance abuse

Introduction

In Pakistan, drug abuse involving illicit substances like heroin and cannabis, as well as non-medical use of prescription drugs, poses a significant challenge to public health and national security. The country addresses this issue through the Control of Narcotic Substances Act of 1997, implementing strict measures to regulate and control drug production, distribution, and consumption.

Pakistan collaborates internationally to combat drug trafficking, aligning with UN conventions on narcotics control. Despite legislative efforts, challenges persist due to socioeconomic factors, regional instability, and porous borders. A holistic approach combining legislation, law enforcement, education, and rehabilitation is crucial to addressing drug abuse effectively and promoting a healthier society. Pakistan significantly reduced opium poppy cultivation in the 1990s, reaching minimal levels in 1999 and 2000 (Song et al., 2024).

In September 2007, the governments of Pakistan and the United States inked a five-year pact to counter drug-related concerns. To combat drugs, several organizations collaborate, including the Airport Security Force, Pakistan Coast Guards, Pakistan Customs, Police, Pakistan Rangers, and Frontier Corps (FC). Pakistan's Anti-Narcotics Policy is formulated and coordinated by the Ministry of Narcotics Control (Nadeem et al., 2024). However, society and the government must work together to address the underlying causes of drug issues (Javed et al., 2023).

Promoting a socioeconomic climate and attitudes that restrict the space for drug misuse is necessary to battle drug abuse successfully (Ochani et al., 2023).

Regarding international collaboration, the strategy promotes involvement in bilateral, regional, and global initiatives to combat drug use. It emphasizes the significance of measures to reduce demand in destination nations and lays particular emphasis on treating the problem at its root in poppy-growing countries (Bryson & Boxhorn, 2023).

The policy seeks to make a substantial contribution to the joint effort to establish a drug-free environment by implementing a comprehensive strategy and promoting global cooperation. In an attempt to lessen the adverse effects drug trafficking and substance misuse have on Pakistan's health, society, and economy, the government has unveiled a new strategy with several goals centered on international collaboration, supply reduction, and demand reduction. This policy addresses the complicated problem of drug-related issues in a way consistent with global best practices (Kardas, 2023).

The Government of Pakistan (GOP) is a signatory to all UN drug control agreements, including the SAARC Convention on Drug Control. It also actively participates in international collaboration for counter-narcotics projects. To jointly work towards establishing a drug-free Pakistan, the GOP is dedicated to collaborating closely with the UN and other international partners. To maintain Pakistan's reputation as a poppy-free nation, ending poppy farming is a crucial goal in the fight against the drug supply (Lika, 2023).

Precursor chemicals, psychotropic substances, and narcotic drug trafficking are further areas of emphasis for the policy. Law enforcement organizations are being strengthened to meet these objectives, and their operations are streamlined to

provide a more efficient response to drug-related problems (Lin et al., 2023).

Research Justification

Research on drug abuse in Pakistan is justified by the urgent need to address a pervasive and complex public health issue with far-reaching consequences. The prevalence of drug abuse poses significant challenges to individual well-being, societal stability, and economic development. Understanding the root causes, patterns, and risk factors specific to the Pakistani context is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies.

Moreover, research can inform evidence-based policymaking, guiding the allocation of resources and shaping legislative frameworks to combat drug abuse. By investigating the impact of cultural, socioeconomic, and geopolitical factors, the research contributes to a nuanced understanding that can lead to targeted and contextually relevant solutions. Justifying research in this area underscores its potential to enhance public health outcomes, reduce social disparities, and contribute to Pakistani communities' overall well-being and resilience.

Research Methodology

This research was formed by a systematic review method. The research objectives are determined by this method, and an extensive literature review is conducted on the subject (Komba & Lwoga, 2020). The research findings are classified according to the subject's content (Hiver et al., 2021; Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). Classified information is included in the study by organizing it as headings (Gan et al., 2021; Pawson et al., 2005). The study flow is based on evaluating classified information and titles (Page, 2021; Rahi, 2017). Thus, integrity is ensured

by evaluating the researched subject's contents (Egger et al., 2022; Victor, 2008). Consequently, this technique was selected, and the associated processes were observed. Reviewing the relevant literature resulted in accumulating data and information coded according to the study goals. The coded data were grouped by subject. After classifying and merging the subjects, they were ordered by degree of connection.

Research Objectives

The research on drug abuse in Pakistan aims to achieve several key objectives. Firstly, it seeks to comprehensively assess the current prevalence and patterns of drug abuse across different regions and demographic groups in Pakistan. Understanding the socioeconomic, cultural, and environmental determinants contributing to drug abuse is crucial. Secondly, the research aims to identify the specific types of drugs commonly abused and analyze their impact on public health. Additionally, the research endeavors to investigate the efficacy of existing preventive and intervention measures, identifying gaps and areas for improvement. By exploring the underlying causes and risk factors, the study intends to contribute valuable insights for developing targeted and culturally sensitive strategies. Ultimately, the research seeks to provide evidence-based recommendations to policymakers and stakeholders, facilitating the formulation of effective policies and interventions to mitigate the adverse effects of drug abuse on individuals and communities in Pakistan.

Literature Review

An estimated 200 million people globally, or around 5% of the population between the ages of 15 and 64, use drugs regularly (Shao et al., 2023). Remarkably, in

the year preceding the 2006 evaluation, the most often used drugs were opiates (0.4%), amphetamines (0.6%), and cannabis (3.8%) (Rockhil et al., 2023). With 162 million users, cannabis is the most commonly used drug. Thirty-five million people take amphetamines, opiates in general, 16 million people, and heroin 11 million people (Bano et al., 2023).

Apart from alcohol and tobacco, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) states that opiates are the primary drug problem worldwide, especially in Asia. 62% of treatment requests in Asia in 2003 were related to opiate addiction (UNODC, 2005). The PAIT countries—Pakistan, Afghanistan, Iran, and Turkey—contribute considerably to the worldwide population of opiate users, although making up just 5% of the world's population. The world's most significant producer of opiates is acknowledged to be the Golden Crescent area, which includes Pakistan and Afghanistan (Shao et al., 2023).

The path taken by opiate traffickers from Afghanistan mostly passes through Pakistan, Iran, Turkey, and the Balkan nations en route to distribution hubs in Western Europe. Nonetheless, signs of new routes developing along the Balkan route to Western Europe, such as the route via Ukraine to Romania. National data from Pakistan, Iran, and Afghanistan indicate an increase in opium use in these countries, despite international data suggesting that steady worldwide opium users numbered 0.4% of the population aged 16–64 during 2004/2005 (Bartolome & Dorneanu, 2023).

Given the significant efforts made in these countries toward supply reduction methods, a thorough analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of these initiatives

is necessary. The current literature review focuses on comparing the demographics of drug users throughout Pakistan and critically examining the laws that are in place to punish those who violate them. Opium has long been produced in Pakistan, both domestically and for export. Production dates back many centuries. The Pakistani government imposed strict anti-drug laws in 1979 in reaction to the growing illegal opium trade (Aslam, 2023).

These laws forbade the trafficking, funding, and possession of drugs over certain thresholds. It included outlawing the growing of poppies, which resulted in the shutdown of all government-run opium processing facilities and sale establishments. As a result, from 9441 hectares in 1992 to less than 284 hectares in 1999, there was a significant drop in the production of opium. Even with strict law enforcement and efforts to reduce supply, drug misuse remains a significant problem in Pakistan (Pain, 2023).

There has been a spike in heroin usage since the 1980s, when the prohibition on legal drug stores did not wholly eradicate the availability and use of illicit drugs. Estimating the overall population of drug abusers at 4 million, the 'National Survey on Drug Addiction' was carried out in 1982, and later studies revealed a significant growth tendency in drug addiction. Recent data shows that drug usage is shifting from smoking to injecting, with the percentage of those using injectable heroin rising from 1.8% in 1993 to 15% in 2000 (Stephenson et al., 2023).

In 2002, a United Nations report claimed that 500,000 people in Pakistan were chronic heroin addicts, of whom 60,000 used injectable heroin. With the enactment of the Narcotic Chemicals (Amendment) Bill of 2022, the Control of Narcotic Drugs Act

(CNSA) in Pakistan has recently undergone substantial modifications that target offenses associated with the trafficking of psychoactive chemicals and narcotics. By introducing the prospect of the death penalty or life in prison, these measures seek to rectify inequities in drug-related justice (Jamshed & Bakhsh, 2023).

This research explores the significant changes brought about by the Control of Narcotic Drugs (Amendment) Act of 2022 and its possible influence on sentencing, focusing on drugs such as heroin, morphine, cocaine, and methamphetamine. The proposed modifications, currently discussed, suggest heightened penalties for violations occurring near educational facilities. The newly named Control of Narcotic Drugs (Amendment) Act of 2022 signifies the president's approval and underscores its comprehensiveness in dealing with drug-related offenses (Jamshed & Bakhsh, 2023).

Notably, the revisions propose severe penalties for heroin and morphine-related offenses, prescribing a minimum 20-year term and a fine of at least Rs. 1 million for quantities weighing 4kg or more. The legislation specifies that larger quantities (6 kg or more) may warrant a life sentence or the death penalty, along with a fine ranging from Rs. 1.5 million to Rs. 2 million.

The Act expands its purview to include cocaine offenses as well, stating that five kilograms or more of the drug may result in the death penalty or life in prison, along with a minimum 20-year term and a fine of at least Rs. 2.5 million (Jawale, 2023). The revisions also deal with offenses using methamphetamine, sometimes referred to as "Ice," where possession of 4 kg or more carries a required punishment of at least Rs. 2.5 million and a sentence of execution or life imprisonment (Jamshed & Bakhsh, 2023). Much more work has to be done to completely eradicate the problem of

substance usage in Pakistan, even if these legal reforms show that the government is taking a proactive approach to fighting drug-related offenses. Despite these endeavors, addressing the complex issues raised by drug usage in Pakistan would require ongoing efforts and a comprehensive strategy.

Drugs

Drug abuse involves the intentional and excessive use of psychoactive substances, such as narcotics like opium and morphine, to alter behavior, mood, or mental state. While some medications are meant for legitimate medical reasons, misuse occurs when substances are taken beyond recommended or prescribed limits, leading to harmful physical and mental consequences. Drug abuse can result in various effects, including pain numbing, behavioral changes, mood swings, and, in severe cases, stupor, coma, or convulsions (Baron et al., 2023).

Difference between Drugs and Narcotics

The physiological and legal settings of drugs and narcotics differentiate them from one another. "Drugs" is a general phrase that includes any drug that affects how the body or mind functions, whether it is legal or not. It covers illegal narcotics, over-the-counter pharmaceuticals, and prescription drugs. However, "narcotics" mainly refers to drugs that can induce sleep or relieve pain; these drugs are frequently connected to opiates like heroin or morphine (Baron et al., 2023).

Although they make up a subset of all medicines, not all substances are classified as narcotics. The legal and medical systems in a particular area are frequently categorizing factors (Stang, 2023).

Drugs Classification

Based on their impact and consumption, drugs may be classified into many groups due to their varying impacts on the human body.

- 1. Depressants:** The human body uses depressants as a slow-down method. Doctors frequently recommend these medications to treat aggression and anxiety, but they can also be abused. People who abuse depressants may be looking for relaxation and an escape from the stresses of everyday life. Because these drugs induce sleep, those who have insomnia may also get addicted to them (Pavarin et al., 2022).
- 2. Hallucinogens:** These drugs cause mood swings and cause users to see and feel things that are not real. Drugs like LSD are notable examples since they can significantly alter sensory experience (Murray et al., 2022).
- 3. Inhalants:** When inhaled, inhalants give out an instant high that causes feelings of lightheadedness, drowsiness, and disorientation. Glue and petrol are two common examples, both of which have the potential to be hazardous and addictive (Tarantino et al., 2022).
- 4. Narcotics:** Although opioids, which are often doctor-prescribed medications, are intended to alleviate pain, they can also cause users to become less conscious and attentive. Some drugs, like heroin, are illegal and very addictive, whereas other drugs are controlled and lawful (Yunus et al., 2022).
- 5. Stimulants:** Stimulants provide users with a mentally and physically energizing impact that produces a euphoric or "high." Methamphetamines

and cocaine are two examples that have the opposite effect on people as depressants (Dominik et al., 2022).

Drugs Substances that Lead to Addiction

Addiction is a broad field that includes many illegal drugs and substances. Addressing the complicated problem of drug addiction requires an understanding of these drugs and their propensity for addiction.

1. **Cannabis:** Also referred to as marijuana, cannabis is the most widely used illegal drug in the world. Although cannabis has long been acknowledged for its therapeutic benefits, it can become addictive and cause altered perceptions, mood swings, elevated heart rate, increased hunger, and decreased blood pressure (Kumar et al., 2021).
2. **Amphetamine-type Stimulants (ATS):** ATS medications stimulate the neural system and cause elevated moods, confidence, and vigor. ATS medicines are risky; their global usage population ranges from 14 to 52.5 million (Makanza, 2021).
3. **Opioids:** Among the earliest psychotropic substances are opioids, especially heroin. Opioids attach to the neurological system, which causes addiction and is a significant factor in drug-related problems (Jain, 2021).
4. **Cocaine:** Dependency on cocaine can cause physiological problems, melancholy, drowsiness, psychosis, and, in severe situations, an overdose that results in death (Graczyk et al., 2021).

5. **Non-Medical Use of Prescription Drugs:** People are increasingly abusing tranquilizers and sedatives for relaxation and momentary solace from despair and other worries in the outside world (Riley, 2021).

Drug Abuse in Pakistan from a Historical Perspective:

Drug misuse has a lengthy and complicated history in Pakistan, especially concerning opium and other narcotics. The Mughal and British empires are the sources of both drug usage and opium manufacturing in the area. Opium, in particular, has played a vital role in the historical custom of drug use over the years. Starting in 1979, Pakistan's opium production saw a noticeable increase. However, the Hadd Ordinance's adoption that same year resulted in a production decline that lasted into the 1980s (Atif et al., 2020).

Afghanistan is essential to Pakistan's extensive drug production and abuse since it is one of the world's top producers of illegal opium. Owing to their proximity, drug abuse and trafficking have increased in Pakistan. Together, Afghanistan and Pakistan generated about half of the world's heroin in the late 1980s, solidifying their position as critical actors in the world drug trade. Despite declining relative shares over time, both nations continue to be significant manufacturers of pharmaceuticals (Atif et al., 2020).

The country's persistent problems with drug usage are exacerbated by Pakistan's key position as an opium transit route from Afghanistan and its proximity to opium farming along the shared border. Pakistan continues to struggle with long-term drug-related issues even after ratifying the 1971 Vienna Convention, which tries to govern international cooperation in reducing the manufacture, distribution,

and use of drugs (Lai & Stoicescu, 2020).

One measure taken to combat drug consumption has been to temporarily reduce the number of poppies grown through alternative development initiatives supported by domestic and foreign funding sources. The Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) have been highlighted as problematic areas for poppy growing, highlighting the ongoing difficulties and complexity of the past and current problems surrounding drug misuse in Pakistan (Atif et al., 2020).

Pakistan's Drug Control Issues and Disparities-Critique on the Control of Narcotic Substances Act

Pakistan is confronted with a complex drug issue that affects more than 6 million individuals grappling with addiction, with a considerable proportion of them already serving prison sentences. Beyond isolated incidents, the problem involves widespread violence that affects families and communities as a result of drug use and commercial distribution. The more significant issue is that drug traffickers and cartels, who finance and oversee the drug trade, enjoy political and criminal impunity (Rosen et al., 2019). While attempts to halt and restrict drug cultivation at home have been effective, policymakers have concentrated on controlling drug trafficking both domestically and internationally.

Enacted in 1997, the Control of Narcotic Substances Act (CNSA) prescribes severe punishments for a variety of drug-related offenses. However, its dependence on charging people for things they physically own paints a false picture of its efficacy. The perception that the domestic drug war is insufficient is influenced by the fact that all offenses carry the same consequences despite their

designation as unique ones (Girelli, 2019).

The Foundation for Fundamental Rights raised concerns about the CNSA, stressing that instead of going after drug mules and couriers with harsh penalties, law enforcement should focus on kingpins. Studies show that just 29% of CNSA investigations with viable leads are followed upon, and 70% of cases never identify kingpins. In addition, those who commit these crimes are frequently extremely poor and illiterate, which leaves them open to exploitation by cartels (Palacios, 2019).

The CNSA has two related problems: it places too much emphasis on the accusation of possession, which lowers the burden of proof, and it gives the accused the duty of proving their guilt rather than the prosecution. It has unfair practical ramifications in addition to breaching the Constitution's guarantees of due process and a fair trial. The current version of the legislation has absurdities that limit its ability to address Pakistan's intricate drug issue (Khaitan, 2019).

Significant Modifications to the Control of Narcotic Drugs Act of 2022

The Control of Narcotic Drugs Act (CNSA) in Pakistan has undergone substantial modifications as a result of the Narcotic Chemicals (Amendment) Bill, 2022, which focuses on offenses associated with the trafficking of psychoactive chemicals and narcotics. The reforms attempt to remedy discrepancies in drug-related justice by allowing the death sentence or life imprisonment. With an emphasis on drugs, including heroin, morphine, cocaine, and methamphetamine, this analysis looks at the main changes made by the Control of Narcotic Drugs

(Amendment) Act of 2022 and how they could affect sentencing (Dollar, 2019).

The proposed modification, presently being discussed, would increase the repercussions for infractions close to educational facilities by imposing harsh penalties. The Control of Narcotic Drugs (Amendment) Act of 2022 is the new name for the legislation, which was approved by the president and highlights how comprehensive it is in handling drug-related offenses. The revisions, in particular, propose severe punishments for heroin and morphine-related offenses, including a minimum term of 20 years and a fine of at least Rs. 1 million for amounts weighing 4 kg or more (Miron et al., 2019).

The legislation stipulates that more significant quantities (6 kg or more) carry a life sentence in jail or the death penalty, in addition to a fine of between Rs 1.5 million and Rs 2 million. The Act broadens its scope to include offenses using cocaine and stipulates that amounts weighing five kilograms or more may result in the death sentence or life in prison. A minimum 20-year sentence and a fine of at least Rs 2.5 million are associated with this. The revisions also deal with crimes using methamphetamine, also referred to as "Ice," which carries a death sentence or life in prison if 4 kilograms or more is found in possession. The law also stipulates that a punishment of at least Rs 2.5 million must be paid (Saingam, 2018).

Legal Perspectives and Persistent Difficulties in Drug Labelling and Penalties under CNSA

Critics point out that Pakistan's Control of Narcotic Substances Act (CNSA)

disproportionately punishes users for not making a distinction between hard and soft drugs. One kilogram or more of both heroin and marijuana is punishable by life in prison or the death sentence under Section 9 (c) of the CNSA. Global trends emphasize the significance of these disparities, yet such a blanket approach ignores the significant variances in the detrimental impact these drugs have on society and health (Uddin & Rahman, 2020). Higher courts in Pakistan, such as the Lahore High Court's special panel in case PLD 2009 Lahore 362, acknowledged the necessity of addressing drug categories in response to this issue.

The court highlighted that the damage and risk associated with different illicit substances covered by the CNSA vary greatly. Sentencing should not be based solely on quantity because a large amount of one drug may not be as harmful as a tiny amount of another. The court emphasized that imposing penalties based on the amount of drugs detected might lead to oppressive and unfair effects (Zunkel & Siegler, 2020).

Even with these judicial insights, the CNSA must adopt these views more broadly. The standards are frequently disregarded by courts operating under the CNSA, leading to arbitrary and inconsistent punishment. It not only goes against the explicit orders from higher courts but also compromises the legal protections afforded to those accused of drug offenses. The prosecution's incapacity to maintain the more significant interest of justice while ignoring the legal safeguards granted to the accused results from this failure to categorize medicines effectively (Gieseke, 2020). The main problem still exists, undermining the CNSA's efficacy and sustaining Pakistan's unfair drug-related justice system.

The Ephedrine Problem-Exposing Pakistan's Methamphetamine (Ice Crisis)

Methamphetamine, also referred to as 'ice,' is a robust artificial stimulant that acts on neurotransmitters in the brain to produce sensations of alertness and exhilaration. Public health is seriously threatened by its increasing prevalence over the world, especially in East and South Asian nations. Similar to other addictive substances, ice was first used medicinally before developing into a lethal weapon that was extensively employed for strategic reasons during World War II (Peacock et al., 2018).

Methamphetamine is unique due to its availability and simplicity in production utilizing everyday household products. Its energy-boosting qualities are partly attributed to pseudoephedrine and ephedrine in over-the-counter cold remedies. The substance may be taken in several ways, the most popular being smoking. Other methods include drinking, ingesting, snorting, injecting, and smoking (Rajabi et al., 2018).

Like other psychoactive substances, prolonged use of ice causes tolerance, requiring higher dosages to get the same effects. Approximately 269 million individuals worldwide, or 5.4% of the world's population, have taken drugs at least once, according to the World Drug Report of 2020. Methamphetamine was one of the amphetamine-type stimulants (ATS) used by about 27 million individuals in 2019, making up almost 0.5% of the adult population (Wang et al., 2018).

The National Assessment Report from 2013 states that 6.5 million drug users are registered in Pakistan, which is also struggling with a severe drug pandemic. With 11% of the population abusing drugs, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is the province most afflicted. The growth in ice use further complicates matters since organizations tasked with reducing drug use have found it difficult to contain the development of addiction in our culture (Saunders et al., 2017).

Notably, the region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has seen an increase in the use of ice among young men and women. The drug's accessibility, lack of knowledge about its toxicity, local production, and appeal to peer groups are all contributing factors. This worrying trend is having serious societal repercussions since young people without jobs are more likely to commit crimes and use illegal ways to support their addictions (Brennan et al., 2017).

The ephedrine problem worsens, resulting from local manufacturing and ineffective government enforcement. The disregard for this growing issue endangers not only the lives of individuals but also presents a severe risk to Pakistani society as a whole.

Discussion

The distinction between drugs and narcotics lies in both physiological and legal contexts. The broad term "drugs" encompasses substances affecting body or mind function, legal or not, ranging from over-the-counter pharmaceuticals to illegal narcotics. Narcotics specifically pertain to substances inducing sleep or pain relief, often associated with opiates like heroin or morphine. Legal and medical systems primarily influence their categorization.

Classifying drugs based on impact and consumption yields categories such as depressants, hallucinogens, inhalants, narcotics, and stimulants. Each category has distinct attributes and potential hazards. Addiction, a complex issue, involves substances like cannabis, amphetamine-type stimulants, opioids, cocaine, and non-medical use of prescription drugs.

In the historical context of Pakistan, drug misuse, especially involving opium, has deep roots dating back to the Mughal and British empires. Afghanistan's role as a major producer of illegal opium contributes to Pakistan's persistent drug-related problems. Despite efforts, issues persist, exacerbated by the country's strategic position as an opium transit route.

Critiques of Pakistan's drug control measures, particularly the Control of Narcotic Substances Act (CNSA), highlight disparities in penalties and the focus on possession over targeting kingpins. The CNSA's recent amendments aim to address these concerns, proposing severe penalties for offenses near educational facilities and escalating consequences for heroin, morphine, cocaine, and methamphetamine-related offenses.

However, critics argue that the CNSA still disproportionately punishes users without distinguishing between hard and soft drugs. Despite judicial recognition of the need for categorization, inconsistencies persist, undermining legal protections and contributing to an unjust drug-related justice system. The rise of methamphetamine (ice) in Pakistan poses a significant public health threat, driven by its availability, ease of production, and increasing use among the population. The ephedrine problem exacerbates this crisis, reflecting local manufacture and inadequate government

enforcement, endangering lives and posing a broader societal risk.

Conclusion

The discourse on the difference between drugs and narcotics highlights the diverse classifications and impacts these substances have on individuals and society. The comprehensive classification of drugs, ranging from depressants to stimulants, underscores the complex nature of substance use and its potential consequences. The discussion on substances leading to addiction, such as cannabis, amphetamine-type stimulants, opioids, cocaine, and non-medical use of prescription drugs, emphasizes the broad spectrum of addictive substances and the need for nuanced approaches to address each.

The historical perspective on drug abuse in Pakistan sheds light on the longstanding challenges faced by the country, particularly about opium and narcotics. The geographical proximity to Afghanistan and the historical context of drug production and abuse contribute to the persistent issues surrounding drug misuse.

The critique of Pakistan's Control of Narcotic Substances Act (CNSA) reveals systemic flaws and disparities in the legal framework, with a focus on the need to target kingpins rather than low-level offenders. The recent modifications proposed by the Narcotic Chemicals (Amendment) Bill, 2022 suggest an attempt to address inequalities in drug-related criminal justice, particularly with severe penalties for heroin, morphine, cocaine, and methamphetamine-related offenses.

The discussion on the Ephedrine problem and the escalating methamphetamine crisis in Pakistan underscores the urgent need for effective government enforcement and awareness programs. The prevalence of methamphetamine, or "ice," poses a severe threat to public health and societal well-being.

In conclusion, while legislative modifications may signal a step towards resolving drug-related issues, addressing the intricate challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes legal reforms, effective enforcement, public awareness, and international cooperation. Pakistan must navigate these complexities to mitigate the adverse consequences of drug abuse and protect its citizens from the growing threats posed by addictive substances.

Research Limitations

Research on drug abuse in Pakistan faces several limitations. Firstly, obtaining accurate and comprehensive data on drug abuse is challenging due to underreporting, stigma, and the illicit nature of the activities involved. Official statistics may not fully capture the extent of the issue. Secondly, the dynamic and evolving nature of drug abuse patterns makes it difficult to establish long-term trends. Additionally, certain regions' socio-political landscape and security concerns may impede researchers' access to affected populations. Moreover, the effectiveness of interventions and policies may be challenging to evaluate, given the complex interplay of cultural, economic, and legal factors. These limitations underscore the need for a nuanced and context-specific approach to understanding and addressing drug abuse in Pakistan.

Research Implications

Research on drug abuse in Pakistan has significant implications for policy and intervention strategies. Understanding the nuanced socio-cultural contexts influencing drug abuse patterns can guide the development of targeted prevention and treatment programs. Identifying high-risk populations and regions enables allocating resources where they are most needed. Additionally, research can inform the adaptation of international best practices to align with local norms and values. Evaluating the effectiveness of existing policies and interventions helps policymakers refine and improve strategies.

Furthermore, insights into the role of socioeconomic factors, educational programs, and community engagement can contribute to holistic approaches to mitigating drug abuse. Collaborative efforts between researchers, policymakers, and community stakeholders are essential for implementing evidence-based solutions and fostering a comprehensive and culturally sensitive response to the complex issue of drug abuse in Pakistan.

Future Research Directions

Firstly, there is a need for enhanced collaboration between government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and international partners. A unified effort is necessary to strengthen law enforcement, improve border control measures, and disrupt the supply chains of illicit substances. Simultaneously, investment in intelligence gathering and sharing mechanisms can facilitate proactive interventions.

Secondly, emphasis should be placed on preventive strategies, particularly in educational institutions. Implementing evidence-based drug education programs can equip young people with the knowledge and skills to resist substance abuse. Public awareness campaigns Utilizing various media channels can also play a pivotal role in changing societal attitudes toward drug use.

Thirdly, a robust healthcare system is essential for providing accessible and effective treatment for individuals struggling with substance abuse. Investment in rehabilitation centers, mental health services, and community-based support networks can contribute to successful recovery and reduce the relapse rate.

Lastly, policy reforms are necessary to balance punitive measures with a focus on rehabilitation. Decriminalization of certain substances for personal use, coupled with a shift towards a health-centered approach, can encourage individuals to seek help without fear of legal repercussions. Addressing drug abuse in Pakistan requires a multifaceted strategy encompassing law enforcement, prevention, treatment, and policy reforms. By fostering collaboration and prioritizing long-term solutions, Pakistan can work towards a future where the impact of drug abuse is significantly mitigated.

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